

**Rethinking Secondary Music Education:
Embracing DAWs as Distinct Student-Centered Learning Tools**

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Abstract

Digital technologies are more important in musical learning than ever before. The global covid-19 crisis of 2020 has uprooted bands, orchestras and choirs from their classrooms and rehearsal spaces, and left teachers pondering effective ways for students to create, perform, and respond musically. The global pandemic in conjunction with rapidly evolving musical technologies has provoked the rethinking of secondary music education traditions. This paper serves a philosophical exploration into digital audio workstations (DAWs) as distinct student-centered tools for musical learning. Both epistemological and learning style (VAK) theories are applied within a student-centered framework in effort to reveal the software's full potential in catering to students' needs. Moreover, DAW's capacity to provide musical scaffolding, support creativity, and enable formative assessments for teachers are discussed. Conclusions suggest that DAWs may have the potential to play a transformative role in secondary music education in times of online learning and beyond.

Keywords: digital audio workstation, music education, music technology, student-centered learning

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In 2020, a global pandemic engulfed the nation in a tidal wave of uncertainty; the American school system quickly drifted into uncharted territory. Music education faced a crisis with classrooms and stages vacant, and performances and festival trips canceled. Music educators scrambled to find ways to translate musical learning into a digital medium. This effort is ongoing, but one thing is for sure, new paradigms for music education may be necessary to move forward with musical learning. New limitations on in-person music-making challenge the ways in which music has been traditionally made, taught and conceptualized. The COVID-19 pandemic and the move to digital learning provides music educators with the opportunity to explore new philosophies and technologies that will constitute the most effective teaching practices. Music educators now rely heavily on digital technologies; this provides an opportunity to make assignments, instruction, and assessment, more student-centered than ever before.

This article seeks to elucidate the potential of digital audio workstations (DAWs) as vehicles for student-centered musical learning. The investigation begins at an epistemological level, exploring three core theories for how students learn and retain information; the third theory, titled the 'knowledge-creation' metaphor, proposed by Paavola & Hakkarainen's (2005), will be used to explain the distinct benefits of digital technologies like DAWs in the student learning process. Further, Walter Burke Barbe's learning style theory of Visual Aural and Kinesthetic (VAK) modalities will be applied to explain the ways that DAWs cater to a diversity of learning styles. Moreover, DAWs have the capacity to cater to diverse student interests and assist in creating individualized curriculum to accommodate, thus providing students with a digital space to work within the musical style, genre or musical occupation of their choosing. Lastly, DAWs provide the unique opportunity for educators to view their students' artistic process through an interface that allows for a clear visualization of the various layers of student decision making; for educators, this information is important in making formative assessments, an integral

component in student-centered teaching. The purpose of this paper is not to explain details of how to use the software, but rather to highlight its potential as an underutilized tool for formal musical learning. The paradigm of music education is inevitably changing, and the field is relying more and more on digital learning tools. This article attempts to present DAWs as viable tools for student-centered music learning as educators, administrators, and policy makers look for new ways to adapt in face of music education's shifting landscape.

Student Centered-Learning

Student-centered learning has roots in early 20th century theories of constructivism found at the confluence of writings from scholars like Lev Vygotsky and Jean Piaget, among others (Brown, 2008; Vygotsky, 1978). While constructivism is not a unified theory, its branches of thought can be distilled down to the idea that 'knowledge is constructed by learners as they attempt to make sense of their experiences' (Chang, 2005, p.387). In constructivism students are "actively involved in determining what their own learning needs are and how those needs can best be satisfied" (Chang, 2005, p. 399); consequently, the implications of constructivist learning theory demand that emphasis should be placed on the learner and their specific needs. In education, this requires the teacher to develop a greater understanding of an individual's learning style, motivating interests and previous knowledge to provide students' the opportunity for optimal meaning-construction.

Student-centered learning and teaching propose that "the planning, teaching, and assessment revolve around the needs and abilities of the students" (Brown, 2008, p.30). Further, "the teacher shares control of the classroom, and students are allowed to explore, experiment and discover on their own" (p.30). The teacher is seen as more of a facilitator than an authoritarian force; students are given agency to practice ways of learning that work best for the individual, and therefore become co-creators within the learning process. This style of teaching creates space for students to use their preferential

learning styles to address musical problems, acknowledging that “students who solve their own musical problems often remember more of what they learn” (Brown,2008, p32).

Student Centered-Learning + Technology

Student-centered teaching may sound appealing in theory, but has not always been used in practice. In 2011, scholars Stuart Wise, Janinka Greenwood and Niki Davis explained how this is due to logistical difficulty, although noting that with advancements in technology, it has become not only possible, but more feasible (Wise et al., 2011); almost a decade later, it has become not only more feasible, but in some ways, pedagogically and logistically necessary. Scholars have been speculating about the effects of new technology on education for decades. In a paper from 1997, Hannafin and Land foresaw the capacity for a future of technology-enhanced student-centered learning environments; they described a digital space that supported the organization of interrelated learning themes into meaningful contexts, allowing space for problem solving or orienting goals; moreover, “they provide interactive, complimentary activities that enable individuals to address unique learning interests and needs, study multiple levels of complexity, and deepen understanding. They establish conditions that enrich thinking and learning, and use technology to enable flexible methods through which the processes can be supported” (Hannafin & Land, 1997 p.168).

Now, in 2020, these types of technologies are available, accessible, and ready to be used in music education. Designing student-centered curriculum can be traditionally difficult and time consuming for educators, although as mentioned by Wise (2011), advancements in technology make it more feasible. DAWs qualify as what Hannafin and Land (1997) called technology-enhanced student-centered learning environments, and they have the capacity to be pragmatic student-centered learning tools for educators.

Digital Audio Workstations

A digital audio workstation (DAW) is defined as a Mac or PC running software for processing and editing digital audio. These digital tools have slowly replaced the heavy and space-consuming analog

hardware that had previously been emblematic of a recording studio (Leider, 2004). DAWs are primarily a tool for recording audio and music production. Sonic information is entered into the software through acoustic instruments playing into a microphone, or the playing of digital instruments (like a piano) that transfer MIDI data into the computer, allowing for the manipulation of timbre, articulation, and dynamics. The accessibility of this software has dramatically increased over the years through affordable pricing and freeware; in ways, this shift has democratized the recording industry, with songwriters and composers producing records in their basements and bedrooms. The level of access, even among non-producers and engineers, has exploded over the past decade, now, with each Mac computer coming with a pre-installed DAW (Garageband); it's become a tool not just for recording music, but also for learning how to create it. Interestingly, as Bell (2015) posits, software developers are now playing a role in music education, arguing that, like the limitations of acoustic instruments, the freedoms and limitations of digital instruments (within a DAW) have even played a role in determining composers' creative process and musical output; software programs in a way, are now determining how aspiring musicians learn and conceptualize music.

DAWs have transitioned into the realm of formal and informal music education. DAWs are in many ways a pragmatic approach, economically and practically, to learning music. Scholars like Serafin & Adjorlu (2017) have proposed the incorporation of DAWs and other virtual and augmented reality programs into formal education, citing the difficulties of learning instruments and K-12 budget cuts. In essence, they suggest using digital MIDI as a way to expedite and democratize musical learning. The most popular DAWs for education, common for function and low price point, are Garageband, Soundtrap and Bandlab, but there are a great variety of commercial DAWs available on the market. This article refers to the term DAW generally, in reference to this type of software; while all programs are different, all features referred to exist as core components of all DAWs.

DAWs and Student Knowledge-Creation

There are many ways of “knowing” music, such as through a fretboard, a hand drum, a saxophone, or even a computer. Instruments can act as gateways to knowing music in a specific way. For example, different instruments tend to utilize specific keys, pitch patterns, or intonations depending on their construction. A musician’s relationships to music can be greatly impacted by the inherent limitations of the instrument in conjunction with the given cultural and communal norms surrounding the musical leaning. When viewed as an instrument, DAWs have the same capacity to diversify ways of knowing music. In education, it is important to discuss how knowledge is created, and how epistemological theories intersect with new methods of learning and instruction. Bringing awareness to educator’s personal understanding of how knowledge is created can have a direct effect on students. A study by Wegner & Nuckels (2013) showed how academics’ personal perceptions of knowledge creation informed their intentions and approaches to teaching. This highlights the importance of acknowledging learning metaphors, and further understanding how DAWs have the potential to be powerful educational tools.

Paavola & Hakkarainen (2005) describe an “emergent epistemological approach to learning” (p.535) called the “knowledge-creation metaphor;” it’s congruent with constructivist learning theories and provides an explanation of the unique knowledge-creation role that DAWs play in enhancing student’s classroom learning experience. This new learning metaphor encompasses and compliments established theories and describes a unique process of knowledge creation through a “mediating artifact.”

There are two generally held beliefs about how humans create knowledge; the first is ‘the acquisition metaphor,’ referred to as monological, and relying on the idea that “knowledge is a property of an individual mind; the individual is the basic unit of knowing and learning (Paavola, 2005, p.538).” This metaphor is prevailing in the university system, perpetuating the paradigm that success is a product of the individual, through evaluative concepts of testing and grades (Wegner & Nuckels, 2013). In music education, this could manifest in assessments such as individual tests on rhythm or scale knowledge. The

second, is ‘the participation metaphor,’ referred to as dialogical, “where learning is an interactive process of participating in various cultural practices and shared learning activities that structure and shape cognitive activity in many ways” (p.539). In music education this metaphor manifests in the evaluation of academic ensembles or any other social or collaborative endeavor. These two metaphors may seem in opposition, but in fact they overlap; we need them both, as Sfard (1998) warned, “too great a devotion to one particular metaphor can lead to theoretical distortions and to undesirable practices (p.4).”

In Paavola & Hakkarainen’s (2005) “emergent epistemological approach to learning,” they outline a ‘triological’ way of understanding learning, theorized and deemed ‘the knowledge-creation metaphor,’ this metaphor is concentric with the previous two, and deemed triological for its inclusion of a third element, that of a mediating artifact (usually a piece of technology); the metaphor involves students working collaboratively with the mediating artifact to create knowledge. Moreover, this triological metaphor becomes practically relevant through the use of specific technologies that help individuals and their communities to jointly work for the advancement of knowledge.

This new knowledge-creation metaphor elucidates the distinct epistemological strengths of DAWs as learning tools or ‘artifacts’ for students to develop alternative ways of knowing music. This ‘advancement of knowledge’ occurs through the process of using DAWs as a space for knowledge building during the creative and collaborative process of recording, editing, and manipulating sound. The process is paramount in understanding the efficacy of DAWs as practical digital classroom tools. As an example, education-specific DAWs like Spotify’s new Soundtrap program allow students to collaborate on remote ‘sessions,’ recording, creating, mixing and mastering independently and together, with artistic decisions collectively proposed, negotiated and defined. Students record, manipulate and listen back to waveforms, only to alter the sounds again, cutting, pasting, and tweaking, with each adjustment as a reaction to the current sonic manifestation. The software provides a specific type of learning for students that involves musical creation and problem solving individually and collectively, but also through

provoking interactions with the software itself—interactions that would not have happened otherwise. DAWs are a mediating artifact that provide a distinct advantage in helping students create musical knowledge.

Learning Styles

On a philosophical level, DAWs have the capacity to help students create musical knowledge in the classroom in a way that has not been possible before. On a practical level, DAWs possess tools that allow for the accommodation of diverse learning styles. The sight of music students with their band or orchestra instrument of choice, attentively looking at their music stands, reading through pages of western music notation, and repeatedly playing phrases to reach a sense of perceived perfection is synonymous with secondary school music education. The path to musical proficiency is clear and codified. Alternative ways of knowing music and musical learning have historically failed to breach the American secondary school paradigm. The reasons for this are manifold, but often it's due to pragmatism, as a student-centered approach can be logistically difficult (Wise, 2011). Hannafin and Land (1997) assert technology as a solution; they conceptualized technology-enhanced, student-centered ways of teaching with tools that could “establish conditions that enrich thinking and learning, and use technology to enable flexible methods (168)” through which these processes could be supported. Many years later, DAW interfaces actualize these flexible methods Hannafin and Land spoke of; they are designed in a way that make space for a diversity of learning styles, and consequently have the capacity to promote alternative ways of knowing and learning music in the classroom.

Learning style can be defined through a confluence of viewpoints. In cognition, learning style refers to information processing and the creation of perception in order to form concepts and principles (Othman & Amiruddin, 2010; Updating Jantan and Razali, 2002). Psychologically, learning style deals with concentration, and methods of processing and obtaining information, knowledge and experience. Moreover, Lebar and Mansor (2000) label learning style as a preferred way of studying through specific

techniques and strategies. The prevailing theory of learning style is that of visual, aural, reading and kinesthetic (VARK) modalities, first designed by Walter Burke Barbe, and later developed by Fleming (2006). VARK classifies students into four different modes of learning, each based on different overlapping senses—visual, aural, reading and kinesthetic (Norasmah Othman & Amiruddin, 2010). Further, VARK learning style does “not involve intelligence or inherent skill but is closely related to how we acquire or understand information (p 658).” Prior to the current iteration of ‘VARK,’ the term VAK was used, strictly referring to visual, aural, and kinesthetic. For the purposes of DAW learning I will only be using VAK.

DAWs as Student-Centered Learning Tools

“Student-centered instruction is when the planning, teaching, and assessment revolve around the needs and abilities of the students (Brown, 2008).”

The visual interface, auditory output, and kinesthetic input (playing natural instruments or midi instruments for recording) allow DAWs to be utilized differently depending on a student’s learning style; this is an important factor as Pritchard (2009) found that the materials used to teach were responsible for learning outcomes in conjunction with student learning style. Othman and Amiruddin (2010) went further in stating that the “production of teaching materials need to be heavily based on students’ learning style (p.657).” Catering to students’ individual learning style is important, and connected to the larger goal of promoting greater access and opportunity to music learning and participation.

The various facets of the traditional DAW interface provide alternative avenues for understanding and engaging with musical fundamentals for visual, aural, and kinesthetic learners. Further, the interface provides musical scaffolding that lowers the necessary threshold for musical skill in order to participate in creating music. This consequently opens the door to not only using DAWs in secondary music courses, but also in secondary general music classes (little or no musical experience). The word scaffold is used to describe the learning assistance DAWs provide in understanding and participating in musical learning, but

also implies that the skills learned can be translated into a non-digital band and orchestra setting. Examples of the scaffolded visual interface will be organized in their respective VAK modality.

Visual Learners

All DAWs are equipped with visual tools that can provide an alternative way to understand musical concepts for students, such as the beatmaker. Programs like Garageband or Logic also allow for composing with western music notation, but the focus of this section will be to elucidate the less traditional ways of learning, knowing and creating music that become available when working with DAWs. Here, I will investigate three of these tools, including the beat-maker (1.1), piano roll (1.2) and general track layout (1.3).

(Beat-maker in Soundtrap) 1.1

The grid-like interface of the beatmaker translates musical subdivisions into divisible squares, with each square representing a beat. In image 1.1, the meter is 4/4, with the 4 horizontal squares representing 16th notes and the 3 vertical squares representing different percussive instruments and timbres. Students can create a percussion track by clicking various squares and then using the 'playback' feature to hear beats. The visual interface allows students to experiment with what 'sounds good' and derive an artistic decision from that alone; this allows students without technical musical knowledge to

participate, create, and build knowledge of musical fundamentals. Theoretical musical knowledge will enhance the experience and further expedite the beatmaking and expedite the process. The beat-maker provides an alternative model for the visual conceptualization of rhythmic theory, further making space for students who do not sufficiently read music, or lack the skill entirely; this could be especially helpful for secondary general music classes, where students appreciate music (often popular music), but have little or no technical facility with their voice or an instrument. This visual scaffolding of the DAW interface allows for these students to participate in music-making and learn music theory in a way that they could not otherwise.

(Piano-Roll in Soundtrap 1.2)

The piano-roll (Fig 1.2) is to pitch what the beat-maker (Fig 1.1) is to rhythm. Melodies and harmonies are mapped out on a grid like structure, with each box corresponding to a pitch on the keyboard. To enter pitches students can click on the grid or enter the 'midi' information from an external keyboard controller. Duration is represented by the number of boxes filled out in succession on the grid. Articulations, and dynamics can be adjusted through clicking on the note of choice and choosing from a menu of options.

A Note on Decentering Literacy

Similar to the beat-maker, the piano-roll allows students to create melodies and harmonies without the steep learning curve of reading music; this allows for alternative conceptualization of western music theory. The notion of placing emphasis away from literacy is not a new concept. Learning through orality, or “learning by ear” has traditionally been the predominant form of transmission and pedagogy within informal music-making settings (Nolet, 2007). Music notation has never been a prerequisite to musical learning. The imposition of western music notation is deeply rooted in Eurocentrism, and can only be understood in the context of the social world in relation to power and access and social justice. In the words of educational philosopher Maxine Greene (1995), “many of the alienated or marginalized are made to feel distrustful of their own voices, their own ways of making sense, yet they are not provided alternatives that allow them to tell their stories or shape their narratives or ground new learning in what they already know” (p. 111). Moreover, to provide these students alternative options for sense-making, grounding new learning and shaping personal narratives, it may be necessary to provide musical experiences that resonate with students' identities and interests. On the topic of non-musical literacy, (Vygotsky, 1978) worried that students would lose interest unless they find it applicable to their daily lives. Similarly, in music, if students are inspired by or play various popular musics outside of school, which broadly do not involve musical literacy, they may lose interest in school music making and choose not to participate. Given the various barriers that musical literacy can present to musical learning and participation, the concept of decentering literacy in the classroom is inherently student-centered.

Aural Learners

For aural learners, the ‘playback’ feature allows students to use their ear to create, and adjust sounds with the ability to ‘click and drag’ the waveform to adjust each sonic fragment to fit their aesthetic preferences. This tool allows for the creation of music without the learning curve of musical literacy or instrumental proficiency. This is a particularly powerful tool in terms of access to musical learning, as it allows students who have not had the opportunity to become sufficiently skilled in western

classical music principles to participate and engage in a musical life. In conjunction with the ‘track-layout’s clear visual representation of instruments and sounds, students can hear and see, in real-time, what happens to the sounds as they cut, paste and craft musical sequences.

Quantize and Pitch-Correct

As a subset of the playback component, quantize and pitch-correct are two features that provide further scaffolding for those without technical musical skills, as it allows for the refinement of recorded sounds. Quantize gives students the ability to correct inaccurate rhythmic durations, similarly pitch-correct allows for the digital adjustment of frequencies. Features like these help students (regardless of skill level), bridge the gap between what their instrumental technique can produce, and what their musical minds have the capacity to conceptualize. These can be valuable tools, especially activities centered around musical creativity, however they may not be appropriate for lessons focused on refining performance practices.

(Track layout in Soundtrap 1.3)

Kinesthetic

Lastly, DAW learning provides space for kinesthetic learners. In the recording process, students can play live instruments (those found in the bandroom), or midi instruments. At first glance, incorporating DAW learning may sound like it is sacrificing traditional musical learning values for that of

another, although this is not the case. The foundation of DAW learning is recording, manipulating and organizing new sounds, and the primary way of recording (or entering midi data) is through kinesthetically playing a live instrument or a midiinstrument (Fig 1.4) into the program. Therefore, students who have the instrumental proficiency or the desire to play their instrument, will continue to have that opportunity. Moreover, students are now able to listen back, and take a critical lens in viewing their performance as they record their instrumental passages into the computer. This feature could be beneficial to student growth. A study on DAWs in the classroom by Plitchta, (2016) showed that using guided critique, paired with self-reflection of student recordings in the software, Garageband, could be promising as a way of formative-assessment in performance-based music classes.

(Midi Keyboard 1.4)

Making Space for Creativity

The adaptive and scaffolded interface of DAWs allow students to engage with music creatively in ways that are not possible in the traditional bandroom. Musicians have been using music technology to find alternative ways to bypass technical limitations to focus on creativity, for over a century. The iconic American pianist and composer, Irving Berlin, is a prime example. Throughout the first half of the 20th century he composed songs for Broadway and Hollywood with memorable hits like “Alexander’s Ragtime

Band and God Bless America.” Berlin was primarily self-taught, and never ventured beyond the black keys of the piano; he only played in the key of F#.(Britannica, 2020). Berlin used a special transposing piano that allowed him to change the key of the music while still using only the black keys on the piano. 100 years later, the top award winning composers such as Hans Zimmer, Danny Elfman, and Trent Reznor similarly rely on current technology, and use the piano roll and beat-maker tools within DAWs to assist their creative process and musical output, with Hans Zimmer, in a masterclass, even encouraging students to “breakthrough the myth that you can’t create a great Hollywood blockbuster on an iPad” (MasterClass, 2016).

The threshold for musical proficiency needed to create music is significantly lowered through the visual, aural and kinesthetic scaffolding of the DAW interface; it’s much easier to ‘click and drag’ waveforms and midi files than to play a two octave major scale, in-tune, on any instrument. With this in consideration, students can put their focus on organizing sound rather than playing scales in-tune, or practicing a Beethoven passage over and over for weeks on end. What I’m describing is still music-making and musical learning; the distinction is that DAWs provide space for students to channel their creativity and compositional vision in a way that wouldn’t be possible otherwise.

An Individualized Curriculum: Student-Centered Instruction

“Learning is most meaningful when subjects are applicable to the students’ interests, educational needs, and lives in general (Brown, 2008, p31).”

DAWs, specifically, present a modular space for students to rest in their preferred learning style and even work in a preferred genre of music, thereby allowing students to create, as Brown (2008) suggested, a “true relevance in the subject matter”—a key principle of student-centered learning. Creating this relevance is important, and is consistent with adult learning theory which “calls for the design of learning activities to be based on the learners’ needs and interests so as to create opportunities for the learners to analyze their experience and its application to their work and life situations” (Sims & Sims,

1995, p.3). These theories recognize the importance of having congruency between secondary school and the work and life situations that follow graduation; there needs to be a link between student interests and curricular content.

The reality is that western 'art' music literacy and performance may not have application to many music loving secondary school students' 'work or life situations,' and consequently may act as a barrier to participation. This can be especially true for novice musicians who have not received years of musical training. A study by Geringer & McManus (1979) found that the more years of music training students had in formal European 'art' music, the more likely they were to value the music of formal European composers; consequently, students may not see value in the European art music-based school curriculum if they are lacking sustained exposure to the music and musical culture.

Cremata and Powell (2017) see using DAWs and other digital music technologies as student-centered tools for peer collaboration, and as a way to bridge the school and work/ life disconnect stating that "by empowering students to be co-creators of their own network mediated, deterritorialized learning, they might find new pathways to learn and renew their desire to continue to learn outside the boundaries of school walls, extending music education into life-wide/long practices (p.313)." Some of these "pathways" lead to different genres of music. Within the software, students are able to make beats for hip hop, catchy chord progressions for rock songs, use a virtual drummer for a jazz track, or use the built-in synthesizers to score a film project. The opportunity for the exploration of style and genres is endless and allows for individualized assignments that cater to student's interests and ultimately motivate them to participate in school, and more broadly, in music as a life-long endeavor.

There are many different ways of knowing and participating in music, music-making and musical learning that fall outside of prevalent pedagogies and traditions used in American music education; DAWs provide an opportunity to reconceptualize the limitations of prevalent pedagogies. Tobias (2017) captured this point perfectly when positing that "music education's tendency toward cultural reproduction of

existing paradigms of music and musical engagement often limits the potential of technology to support and mediate a broad range of ways people can be musical (Ruthmann & Mantie, 2017, p.292); these ways of being musical don't need to involve an instrument. In the modern music industry, songwriters and composers have multiple titles and responsibilities such as performer, producer and audio engineer; rarely are they limited to just one part of the process. Current technology, and the move to DAWs as the industry standard, have brought about this shift. A study by Tobias (2012) involving songwriting with DAWs exemplifies how using digital audio workstations in the classroom provides the opportunity for students to manifest as 'hyphenated musicians.' Students rose to the occasion when told to make a recording; they took on the various roles inherently involved in production, from songwriting, to arranging, recording, performing and producing (Zak, 2001). The various tasks involved in creating and recording a song were undertaken with an ebb and flow. Not all students participated in all roles, but rather were able to work within singular or overlapping roles that suited them best (Tobias, 2012). The 'hyphenated' musician in the music industry has become commonplace, arguably due to the embrace of digital audio workstations and their capacity to accommodate the whole compositional process from ideological inception to the release of a polished and professional recording. In education, this feature of DAWs gives students the opportunity to explore other, less traditional, ways of being a part of the music making process. Most importantly, this diverse functionality has the capacity to cater to students who are left out of the strictly eurocentric paradigm, and as Clauhs (2019) posited, potentially "widen the door (p.55)" for students who are less interested or less able to participate in orchestra, choir, band or music appreciation electives. In essence, through the incorporation of DAWs, students can learn how they want and what they want while still creating fundamental musical knowledge.

Chronicling Student Learning Process: A New Tool for Formative Assessment

"In student-centered classrooms, students are involved in creating strategies that teachers can use. In fact, some of the best teaching strategies come from students, because the students are the ones that are

being taught. Often no one knows better how students learn than the students themselves (Brown, 2008, p.31).”

A potent and distinct feature of all DAWs is the audible and visual representation of process. From an educational standpoint of assessment, this provides teachers with an unprecedented ability to see into the musical minds of their students, observing their process of decision making individually and collectively, and the ability to observe knowledge creation and learning style. This information can be used for ‘formative assessments,’ where student performance on assignments is then used to influence and change future assignments to better fit student needs (William, 2006).

In every DAW, sonic clips are recorded, and audibly and visually represented in the form of a linear track. Multiple sounds are stacked on top of each other along a timeline, with each alteration to the waveforms captured for educators to see and hear (Fig 1.3). These documented sonic visualizations can provide valuable insight for educators, especially when paired with students’ personal reflections—a pillar of student-centered pedagogy. Further, inherently collaborative DAWs like Soundtrap or Bandlab have dialogue boxes for students to communicate artistic decisions through text about their project, with each conversation preserved for educators to see. Gaining insight into a student’s knowledge creation process is paramount for educators. Teachers can use this insight to most effectively craft future curriculum that will allow all students. In conclusion, DAWs are tools for creating and refining best practices in student-centered musical pedagogy, as they provide space for diverse learning styles to experiment and create, and the ability for teachers to witness.

Final Considerations

In the near future, bands, orchestras, and choirs will resume in schools, and once again fill classrooms and concert stages; music education will resume as students prepare their repertoire for the next concert or festival. The aim of this paper is not to extinguish this tradition, but rather, to elucidate the strengths of alternative paradigms when faced with a crisis. In the past few decades, technology has

advanced at an unprecedented rate, and left music education behind. Digital audio workstations (DAWs) are technologies that provide promise for the future of the field; they are tools for student-centered learning that should be considered by teachers, administrators and policy makers. DAWs have the capacity to assist in providing a distinctive experience for students to create knowledge individually, with their peers, and through interaction with the computer. The software allows students to create knowledge on their own terms by accommodating visual, aural and kinesthetic learners in the musical learning process. Moreover, DAWs make it easier for educators to create individualized curriculums that cater to student's interests while still facilitating musical learning. Finally, DAWs are unrivaled as tools for formative musical assessments; student performances and compositions can be saved audibly and visually in the software, providing windows into student reasoning, creativity and growth. In summation, DAWs have the potential to play a transformative role in the field of music education for times of crisis and beyond.

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